

Evidence-based Approach Using Multivariate Regression Analysis And Machine Learning Algorithms To Discover Optimum Medical Cannabis Compound Ratios For Highest Efficacy And Lowest Side-effects In PTSD Subjects

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Abstract

In the absence of randomized clinical trials, meta-analysis of crowd-sourced consumer data may provide the most accurate understanding of how medical cannabis is currently used by patients in treating various medical conditions. We compared different statistical and data science analytic approaches to determine the specific strains and their relative chemical compositions of THC (Tetrahydrocannabinol) and CBD [1][2], (cannabidiol) with highest perceived efficacy and lowest side effects. Two approaches, standard multivariate regression analysis and machine learning algorithmic models were used to classify, validate and predict the best strains for the specific medical condition of PTSD or Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, a condition that is well known to be relieved by medical cannabis. Our analysis has identified cannabis strains with specific THC / CBD combinations that have the highest overall consumer ratings with lowest side-effects. In this crowd-sourced data meta-analysis, standard multi-variable and machine learning based methods of determining the most effective strain / cannabinoid combination have presented us with statistically significant strain and their chemical compositions which customers are using for PTSD. Our results are summarized on the [website](#)

This research addresses the following issues for the beneficiaries:

- **Customers:** PTSD support groups and focused patient groups would benefit from this analysis as it either validates their existing medical cannabis prescriptions or provides alternatives with the least side effects, without a trial-and-error approach to the plethora of strains available today.
- **Dispensaries:** Dispensaries can use these results to recommend appropriate strains in their inventory for customers with PTSD. They can also match their observational understandings with our study. E.g. if they don't carry a specific strain that is recommended, they can look at varieties in the same category with similar chemical compositions as an alternative.
- **Pharmacologists:** Dispensaries don't have any research around strains, compounds and their effectiveness for specific medical conditions. This research paper provides them the required analysis to ensure their recommendations have a high percentage of efficacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the absence of randomized clinical trials, data from non-experimental crowd-sourced data can shed light on how patients are using medical cannabis to treat specific medical conditions. This evidence based approach to crowd-source data with the right data science models applied against them will help define, classify and predict the efficacy of specific strains and compounds (i.e. THC / CBD currently and other cannabinoids and Terpenes in the future) and their relative side-effects. Data from these observational studies can be pooled to provide an estimate of effect that may be more precise than that obtained by a single study. Without sufficient clinical studies, medical cannabis relies on anecdotal and trial-and-error approach to cannabis strain recommendations and dosage without regard to side effects or patient constitution. Traditional aggregate data meta-analyses, especially of observational studies, have limited capacity to adequately account for factors because of the sparsity of the data

from dispensaries, clinical practitioners and the lack of rigor in the patient feedback collection. While the crowdsourced data we collected contained information on patient usage for many medical conditions, we have narrowed our analysis to just one condition here, specifically PTSD.

A. PTSD: An Introduction

PTSD (Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder) is a severe anxiety disorder caused by experiencing or witnessing a traumatic event, such as combat, a natural disaster, a car accident, or sexual assault. PTSD affects nearly 8% of Americans, or 24.4 million people according to PTSD United [3]. An estimated one out of every nine women develops PTSD, making them about twice as likely as men to suffer from this condition. PTSD can affect all aspects of one's life including mental, emotional, and physical well-being. Symptoms include nightmares, flashbacks, insomnia, hyper vigilance, anxiety, depression, self-destructive behavior and social isolation. Eventually, PTSD interferes and debilitates with one's work and relationships. Many PTSD patients find that cannabis is an effective treatment for both the mental and physical symptoms without the harsh side effects of opioids and psychiatric medications such as Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRI's) and Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SRNI's). However, the THC in medical cannabis can also cause the side effects of anxiety or paranoia. CBD can offset the negative side effects of THC. This is called the "entourage effect". This analysis explores the ideal ratio of CBD to THC for optimum efficacy with the least side effects, specifically for the condition of PTSD.

In the sections to come, the paper has been structured as follows. Section 2 gives an introduction to the data source from which the data has been acquired from for the analysis, and the highlights of the analysis performed. Section 3 describes the Descriptive Analysis performed, Section 4 describes the Statistical Analytics done, Section 5 describes the Machine Learning models run on the dataset, and finally the last section comprises of the Conclusion.

II. DATA SOURCE AND ANALYSES PERFORMED

A. Data Source and Description

A crowd-sourced dataset that provides evidence based features from more than 190,000 product reviews for over 3,000 products. Data sources include product data from industry leading community sites.

Specifically, the snapshot of all data from August 2017 includes:

- 193,000 Total User Submitted Reviews
- 3727 Unique Cannabis Strains
- 19 Direct Psychological and Physiological Effects
- 44 Medical Related Conditions
- 6 Major Psychological and Physiological Side-Effects

B. Analyses Performed

- Statistical analysis to determine how THC and CBD Percentages in the strains and the functional derivatives such as THC/CBD Ratios drive the efficacy of strains for one specific medical condition. Statistical analysis is highly relevant to determine how independent and dependent variables affect the user scoring and to define the customer sentiment sensitivity analysis.
- Natural language processing (NLP) was used to extract from the text reviews specific medical conditions, side effects, efficacy and sentiment. This information is then aggregated and used for training the machine learning models which are used to predict the ideal compound combinations for consumers with PTSD.
- We used a variety of machine learning models to determine which strains have the highest efficacy with the least side effects for PTSD. Model evaluation was based on model accuracy, outlier analysis, sample density/sparsity and generally accepted principles of algorithmic modeling.
- Other than THC and CBD, our dataset did include CBN data. However, it was not available for all strains and the integrity of the data was not clear. We also did not include any terpene information since it was not available in this data extract. We have created a replicable process where information can easily be fed into our analysis engine and new insights can be derived quickly as when terpene information becomes available.

III. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYTICS

A. Data Visualization

Table I illustrates the high level pre-processed subsetted data for PTSD.

TABLE I
TABLE SHOWING SUBSET OF DATA OF STRAINS USED SOLELY FOR PTSD

Medical Condition	Total Reviews in Dataset	Unique strains used by customers for PTSD
PTSD	125714	440

Top 10 Most Popular Strains for PTSD relief

Top 10 Reviewed Strains for PTSD with Lowest Mentioned Side Effects

Fig. 1. Top Strains for PTSD based on Votes and Ratings for PTSD and lowest mentioned side effects

Figure 1 represents the top 10 strains as used by consumers and their relative ranks. Rank is imputed as a function of number of votes and user rating. For example, Gorilla Glue was the most used strain based on its user rating and the total votes. Figure 2 shows CBD percentage versus average THC of different strains for PTSD. The size of the bubbles is proportional to the number of reviews for strains. It is quite apparent that most of the bubbles are clustered around 14%-28% THC and 0-5% CBD.

Fig. 2. CBD Vs. Avg. THC plot of Strains for PTSD

B. Text Analytics

With more than 190,000 text reviews, it was necessary to identify the context within the text so that we can incorporate these as features in our machine learning models. The core dataset did not specifically identify PTSD as a condition. However, consumers did mention in the reviews that they are either currently taking it for PTSD or have taken it in the past with varying levels of effectiveness. The first step of our text analytics was developing a medical terminology corpus and using NLP (Natural Language Processing) engines to extract reviews with medical conditions only and tag these reviews with a binary value so that we can run statistical analysis on them. Assumption - Consumer reviews sometimes might be describing PTSD as a medical condition, but do not directly have the word PTSD in it. Such reviews are not being considered for the analysis.

1) Text Analysis:

The following steps shows the approach taken in our work.

• Step 1: Medical Lingua Corpus Creation

Consumer reviews from websites are intuitive for readers, but a system-based analysis to detect the right medical keywords and context requires a word / phrase dictionary. This corpus of medical marijuana / cannabis terms can be used as a filter for the reviews that have medical value. Furthermore, we can fine-tune the corpus to extract not just words, but phrases. For example, feeling paranoid and did not have paranoia like the last time reflect two opposite sentiments which if we used a standard keyword search algorithm would fail. Hence, contextual search is important for our next step of meta-tagging. The corpus data was extracted from these websites:

- www.emedicinehealth.com
- www.macmillandictionary.com
- www.coloradopotguide.com

Reviews that contain medical terms outside of the above listed websites are not being captured.

• Step 2: Medical Condition Matching

This step was to identify the medical terms present in each individual reviews addressing PTSD. The count of each identified medical terms is aggregated across all reviews. Based on the count, the identified medical terms are ranked to obtain the medical conditions that are strongly correlated with PTSD.

• Step 3: Sentiment Analysis and Keyword Extraction

Sentiment analysis was performed on the user reviews using the natural language toolkit and textblob package in Python. Based on the sentiment score derived from each review, reviews were classified into three groups - positive, negative and neutral. Emotions were derived in each review through an API call to IBM Watson[4]'s natural language understanding. A

Observations: It was observed that whenever a customer is talking about PTSD in the reviews, there is strong correlation with other medical terms such as anxiety, depression, stress, insomnia and nausea.

3) *Word Tree:*

Results of text analysis is visualized in the form of word tree. Font size of the text is proportional to the count (number of reviews which contain that particular medical condition). Figure 5 shows the word tree derived.

Fig. 5. Dendrogram of associated medical conditions

4) *Observation:*

The analysis of the word cluster is as follows:

- Patients suffering from PTSD are more likely to explicitly talk about anxiety and depression. While this may seem straightforward, the reverse may not be true. If we had started the node analysis with anxiety and depression, we may see PTSD as a corollary condition, i.e. severity of the anxiety and depression is not effectively communicated by the consumers in their reviews
- When a patient has PTSD and anxiety issues, they are more likely to have issues with insomnia, stress and depression percentages can affect product rating. The second analysis is only focusing on the reviews mentioned PTSD.

IV. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

A. *Data Preparation*

There are two parts included in the Statistical Analysis. The first part of the analysis looks at how the change in THC and CBD percentages can affect the probability of PTSD to be mentioned in the product reviews. The results of the text analysis was used to synthetically create a new binary/boolean feature or column in the dataset to represent PTSD. This column will contain a value of 1 when the reviews mention PTSD and 0 when there is no mention of PTSD. For the purpose of this analysis, we only included strains where the PTSD feature in [0,1]. We also eliminated data which had 0% THC, which indicated inaccurate source data. This new dataset contains 2,229 products. In the cases where the THC value was provided as a range (e.g. 20%- 24%) and not a specific percentage, THC average is used for these products. The assumption is that once THC reaches a certain percentage threshold, increasing the THC percentage will cause negative effects for the consumers. In order to observe the diminishing return on THC, the quadratic term of THC is included. In this dataset, most of the products contain a relatively higher percentage of THC than CBD.

TABLE II
DATA DESCRIPTION

Variables	Description
<i>THC</i>	The average THC percentage contained in the strain. Typically THC values are a range and therefore a straight average is used for calculations
<i>THC</i> ²	Squared term of THC percentage
<i>CBD</i>	The approximate CBD percentage contained in the strain
<i>CBD/THC</i>	Ratio of CBD and THC average
<i>X4PTSD</i>	Dummy variable of PTSD (1 = users do mention PTSD in the product review, 0 = no mention of PTSD in reviews)
<i>Rating</i>	Customer rating for each strain

TABLE III
STATISTICAL SUMMARY OF THE DATA

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev	Min	Max
<i>THC</i>	2229	01917	0.0495	0.0100	0.4100
<i>CBD</i>	2229	0.0080	0.0291	0.0000	0.4000
<i>CBD/THC</i>	2229	0.2325	1.9568	0.0000	40.000
<i>X4PTSD</i>	2229	0.1862	0.3893	0.0000	1.0000
<i>Rating</i>	2229	4.3390	0.9532	0.0000	5.0000

B. Empirical Result and Discussion

PTSD versus THC and CBD

To observe the effect of change in THC/ CBD on PTSD we use the dummy variable PTSD as the dependent variable and THC/ CBD as the independent variables. We selected the Logit Model since since the dependent variable is a dummy variable.

1) *Logit Model: PTSD vs. THC and CBD*: Equation (1) shows the expression for the Logit Model discussed.

$$X4PTSD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 THC + \beta_2 CBD + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Here, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 , β_2 are the coefficient for each independent variable. ϵ is the error term, which including all other factors that can affect the probability of consumers mentioning PTSD in the product reviews, such as demographic variables. For example, consumer's age, BMI, gender.

Table IV shows the effect of change in THC and CBD on PTSD reviews.

TABLE IV
EFFECT OF CHANGE IN THC, CBD ON PTSD REVIEWS

Dependent Variable	X4PTSD
<i>THC</i>	2.1446 (p = 0.07441) .
<i>CBD</i>	5.2370 (p = 0.00363)**
Intercept	-1.9342
Observations	2229

Since the result gives small p-values, both THC and CBD are significantly correlated with PTSD appearing in customer reviews. Whenever a customer mentions PTSD in the reviews, we infer that THC and CBD are significant within a 90% confidence interval.

Since we are using the Logit model here, interpretation of probabilities requires further calculation.

Figure IV-B1 shows the probability of PTSD appearing in customers' reviews based on different percentage of independent variables.

For example:

- If THC is 1%, the probability of PTSD being mentioned the reviews is 12.87%.
- If THC is 2%, the probability of PTSD being mentioned the reviews is 13.11%.
- If CBD is 1%, the probability of PTSD being mentioned the reviews is 13.22%.
- If CBD is 2%, the probability of PTSD being mentioned the reviews is 13.83%.

The result indicates as CBD increases, the probability of PTSD being mentioned in customers' reviews increase more than compared to THC. As CBD increases from 1% to 5%, the probability increases from 13.22% (increased by 2.59%). As THC increases from 1% to 5%, the probability increases from 12.87% to 13.86% (increased by 0.99%)

2) *Logit Model: PTSD vs. THC, CBD and THC^2 :*

$$X4PTSD = \beta_0 + \beta_1THC + \beta_2CBD + \beta_3THC^2 + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

TABLE V
EFFECT OF CHANGE IN THC, THC^2 , CBD ON PTSD REVIEWS

Dependent Variable	X4PTSD
<i>THC</i>	-2.026 (p = 0.6619)
<i>THC²</i>	11.597 (p = 0.3536)
<i>CBD</i>	4.252 (p = 0.0417) *
Intercept	-1.582
Observations	2229

As the quadratic term of THC added, only CBD remains significant and THC and THC^2 are not significant.

3) *Logit Model: PTSD vs. CBD / THC Ratio:* We now wanted to look at strains and the CBD % and THC % combinations that appear in the PTSD reviews. We then added a ratio variable CBD/THC and categorized the values into 14 discrete bins:

TABLE VI
CBD/THC RATIO IN CATEGORIZED BINS

Bin Name	CBD/THC Range	THC/CBD Range	Number of Observations
GT1	0	0	1793
GT2	(0.01 - 0.039)	(100 - 25.64)	16
GT3	(0.039 - 0.049)	(25.64 - 20.4)	75
GT4	(0.049 - 0.059)	(20.4 - 16.94)	85
GT5	(0.059 - 0.069)	(16.94 - 14.49)	35
GT6	(0.069 - 0.079)	(14.49 - 12.65)	11
GT7	(0.079 - 0.089)	(12.65 - 11.23)	11
GT8	(0.089 - 0.099)	(11.23 - 10.1)	13
GT9	(0.099 - 0.129)	(10.1 - 7.75)	31
GT10	(0.129 - 0.19)	(7.75 - 5.26)	24
GT11	(0.19 - 0.299)	(5.26 - 3.34)	24
GT12	(0.299 - 1.01)	(3.34 - 0.99)	55
GT13	(1.01 - 1.9)	(0.99 - 0.52)	23
GT14	(1.9 - 41)	(0.52 - 0.02)	33

Most of the observations fell into Bin GT1 (CBD/THC=0). Since we eliminated THC=0% from the dataset, this GT1 bin indicates that there are 1793 observations with 0% CBD.

$$X4PTSD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Bin(CBD/THC) + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

Here, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 is the coefficient of CBD and THC ratio. ϵ is the error term.

TABLE VII
TABLE SHOWING SIGNIFICANCE OF BINS

	Coefficients	Pr(> z)	Significance
(Intercept)	-1.62491	<2e-16	***
GT2	1.11409	0.032259	*
GT3	0.93176	0.000232	***
GT4	0.80547	0.000957	***
GT5	0.56404	0.150141	
GT6	0.12083	0.877562	
GT7	1.0653	0.090853	
GT8	0.42094	0.524465	
GT9	-0.02375	0.961539	
GT10	1.11409	0.008985	**
GT11	-0.321	0.604924	
GT12	0.23862	0.486715	
GT13	0.79823	0.081103	
GT14	0.792	0.039213	*

At 90% confidence interval, the bins GT2, GT3, GT4, GT7, GT10, GT13, GT14 are statistically significant. In these bins, GT2 and GT10 both have the highest coefficient (1.11409).

TABLE VIII
RATIOS WHICH ARE SIGNIFICANTLY CORRELATED TO PTSD

Bin	CBD/THC Ratio Range	THC/CBD Ratio Range
GT2	(0.01 - 0.039)	(25.64 - 100)
GT3	(0.039 - 0.049)	(20.4 - 25.64)
GT4	(0.049 - 0.059)	(16.94 - 20.4)
GT7	(0.079 - 0.089)	(11.23 - 12.65)
GT10	(0.129 - 0.19)	(5.26 - 7.75)
GT13	(1.01 - 1.9)	(0.52 - 0.99)
GT14	(1.9 - 41)	(0.02 - 0.52)

4) *OLS Model: Ratings vs. THC and CBD*: The goal of this analysis is to see how changes in THC and CBD affect product ratings. In this analysis, we are focusing on the products with PTSD mentioned in product review, thus PTSD = 1 is the condition. In this case, the subset of PTSD =1 has a total of 415 observations. All the products with 0% THC average are eliminated. Since rating is a continuous variable, this analysis is using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model.

$$rating = \beta_0 + \beta_1 THC + \beta_2 CBD + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

Here, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 , β_2 are the coefficient of THC and CBD. ϵ is the error term, all other factors can affect general product rating beside THC and CBD are included in the error term, such as price of the product and taste of the product.

TABLE IX
OLS MODEL: RATINGS VS. THC AND CBD

Dependent Variable	rating
THC	1.4546 (p=0.0434)*
CBD	1.6735 (p=0.153)
Intercept	4.1789
Observations	415

The intercept indicates if we don't consider the factor of THC and CBD, the general product rating will be 4.17. THC is positively correlated with rating within 95% confidence interval, but CBD is not significant. Thus, if there is a 1% increase in THC of the strain, the product rating increases by 29.1% or 1.455 (on a scale of 1 to 5)

5) *OLS Model: Ratings vs. CBD / THC Ratio*: Extending the earlier model, we now replaced CBD and THC with the CBD/THC ratio to see the compounded effect.

TABLE X
CBD/THC RATIO IN CATEGORIZED BINS BASED ON RATINGS

Bin Name	CBD/THC Range	THC/CBD Range	Number of Observations
GT1	0	0	295
GT2	(0.01 - 0.039)	(100 - 25.64)	6
GT3	(0.039 - 0.049)	(25.64 - 20.4)	25
GT4	(0.049 - 0.059)	(20.4 - 16.94)	26
GT5	(0.059 - 0.069)	(16.94 - 14.49)	9
GT6	(0.069 - 0.079)	(14.49 - 12.65)	2
GT7	(0.079 - 0.089)	(12.65 - 11.23)	4
GT8	(0.089 - 0.099)	(11.23 - 10.1)	3
GT9	(0.099 - 0.129)	(10.1 - 7.75)	5
GT10	(0.129 - 0.19)	(7.75 - 5.26)	9
GT11	(0.19 - 0.299)	(5.26 - 3.34)	3
GT12	(0.299 - 1.01)	(3.34 - 0.99)	11
GT13	(1.01 - 1.9)	(0.99 - 0.52)	7
GT14	(1.9 - 41)	(0.52 - 0.02)	10

$$rating = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Bin(CBD/THC) + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

Here, β_0 is the intercept, β_1 is the coefficient of CBD and THC ratio. ϵ is the error term. The results indicate that only Bins GT7 and GT9 are negatively correlated with rating.

TABLE XI
TABLE SHOWING SIGNIFICANCE OF BINS

	Coefficients	Pr(> z)	Significance
(Intercept)	4.472203	<2e-16	***
GT2	-0.022203	0.934	
GT3	0.187797	0.168	
GT4	0.089335	0.504	
GT5	0.005574	0.98	
GT6	0.227797	0.623	
GT7	-1.022203	0.002	**
GT8	0.294463	0.437	
GT9	-0.752203	0.011	*
GT10	0.183352	0.407	
GT11	-0.105537	0.781	
GT12	0.091433	0.649	
GT13	-0.243632	0.33	
GT14	0.157797	0.453	

The following Bins are significant, and negatively correlated with rating. Table XII shows the same.

TABLE XII
BINS THAT ARE NEGATIVELY CORRELATED WITH RATINGS

Bins	CBD/THC	THC/CBD	N	Coefficient	p-value
GT7	0.079 - 0.089	11.24 - 12.66	4	-1.0222	0.002
GT9	0.099 - 0.129	7.75 - 10.10	5	-0.7522	0.011

If CBD/THC ratio of the product is in bin GT7, and 1% increase in the ratio will cause the product rating to decrease by 1.0222 (20.4%). If the ratio is in bin GT9, a 1% increase in the ratio will cause the product rating to decrease by 0.75 (15%). The strains in statistically significant bins can decrease Rating.

Table XIII below summarizes the strains in each of the statistically significant bins.

TABLE XIII
PRODUCT NAME WITH IT'S SIGNIFICANT BIN

Product Name	Bin
Diesel-duff	GT7
Romulan-grapefruit	GT9
Rocky-mountain-high	GT9
Purple-mr-nice	GT9
Tangerine-haze	GT9
Pure-og	GT7
Skywalker-og	GT7
Og-strawberry	GT7
Jedi-kush	GT7

C. Statistical Analysis Results

- The probability that PTSD appears in the customer review increases more when CBD % increases than THC % increases.
- The result of adding the quadratic term of THC is not reliable in this case. Hence the observation for diminishing returns of increases THC % is inconclusive for this current dataset.
- The top strains by looking at CBD and THC ratio with most reviews are shown in Table XIV

TABLE XIV
TOP STRAINS WITH MOST REVIEWS

Product	Reviews	THC	CBD	CBD/THC	Bin
girl-scout-cookies	55	0.28	0.01	0.357	GT2
gorilla-glue	24	0.265	0.01	0.0377	GT2
bruce-banner	22	0.265	0.01	0.0377	GT2
gods-gift	16	0.27	0.01	0.0370	GT2
holy-grail-og	12	0.265	0.04	0.1509	GT10
blue-knight	12	0.27	0.04	0.1481	GT10

- If CBD/THC ratio of the product is in bin GT7 [0.079,0.089], and 1% increase in the ratio will cause the product rating to decrease by 1.0222 (20.4%). If the ratio is in bin GT9 [0.099,0.129] , a 1% increase in the ratio will cause the product rating to decrease by 0.75 (15%)

V. MACHINE LEARNING

A. Data Preparation

Initial analysis of the data sets contained multiple features for side-effects ranging from headaches, dry mouth, dry eyes to anxiety and paranoia. While each of the features was a numerical value ranging from 1-10, the results of our clustering indicated that results did not take into account the severity of the side effect. For example, paranoia and anxiety were considered more severe side-effects compared to dry mouth and dry-eyes.

TABLE XV
WEIGHTS ASSIGNED TO CONDITION BASED ON SEVERITY

Condition	Paranoia	Dizziness	Anxiety	Headache	Dry Mouth	Dry Eyes
Weights	10	6	4	2	1	1
Natural Log	2.3025	1.7917	1.3862	.06931	0	0

We imputed a side-effect score based on a weights so that side effects will carry a negative value.

B. Unsupervised Learning: Clustering Models

We used the following models to cluster the data so that we can build a regression model more effectively. The lack of any training data means that we used a randomized training set from the core data. The details of each of the model is presented here:

- 1) K-Means
- 2) Fuzzy Clustering
- 3) DBSCAN (density-based)
- 4) Latent Class Analysis
- 5) Sparse Representation

C. Approach Summaries

1) K-Means[7]:

The main goal is to see how chemical composition and negative side effects can be clustered together to find patterns in the data. A primal way of doing this is through an unsupervised learning approach and we have explored using the k-means. K-means is one of the most efficient algorithms in terms of performance and as well as gives a very easy understanding to what the data looks like.

a) **Scaling of Negative side effects:** The negative side effects defined here are: Dry Mouth, Dry Eyes, Headache, Paranoid, Dizzy, Anxious.

- Negative side effects are from a range of 0 to 10 based on how greatly each negative side effect impacted the patient. Higher the score, the worse is the side effect.
- For analysis, each negative side effect was multiplied by a logarithmic value (paranoid : log 10, dizzy: log 6, anxious: log 4, headache: log 2 while dry eyes and dry mouth was given 0) and then later averaged across all side effects followed by normalizing them on a scale of 0 to 1

b) Approach:

Model 1: Using Sativa % and Indica % as features

- The features that are considered here are the chemical compositions and strain features namely Sativa %, Indica % both which are derived from plant parentage, THC % and CBD % and the weighted average of the negative side effects.
- The number of samples related to PTSD was 428

Clustering:

Assumptions : The variance of distribution of each variable is spherical and also all variables have same variance.

- One of the important parameters in k-means is finding the k.
- The k can be found by elbow method through which k was found out to be 3.
- After the k-means clustering is done there were 209 samples in cluster1, 142 samples in cluster 2 and 77 samples in cluster 3.
- Weakness: Stability and choosing the value of k .
- Some Key Observations that could be made after examining each cluster was that Cluster 1 consisted of CBD value of 0 which doesnt help us in identifying the products that we want least negative side effects from and also the least negative side effects were found when Indica is more and sativa less for Cluster 0 and 1 respectively.
- Snapshot of the Box plots for this clustering is shown in the appendix
- The important thing to note is that Cluster 2 had a hybrid mixture of sativa and indica components and higher average side effects with the roughly same amount of CBD and THC as that of Cluster 0.

While there were three clusters, it was not coherent with our main goal of finding products with least negative side effects. Votes was another feature chosen to consider the products with least negative side effects and get better clusters. The“Votes” feature in the dataset signifies how many customers have liked a product. The Votes has been normalized to a scale of 0 to 10.

Model 2: Using Votes as feature.

Features considered: Here Sativa % and Indica % werent selected as features and instead votes was considered. THC represents the Average THC as computed in the statistical analysis section. The final features and their descriptive statistics are shown in Table below

	votes	thc_avg	CBD	Weighted_avg_score
count	428.000000	428.000000	428.000000	428.000000
mean	0.913656	0.182629	0.010818	0.206064
std	0.937591	0.068304	0.031881	0.181204
min	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.298507	0.165000	0.000000	0.082228
50%	0.671642	0.195000	0.000000	0.173803
75%	1.268857	0.225000	0.010000	0.302758
max	10.000000	0.410000	0.240000	1.000000

Clustering:

As described earlier the value of K in cluster initialization can be found by Elbow method. The plot can be seen in the Appendix where k can be chosen to be either 4 or 5. A cluster 3 had some very high variance for some of the clusters and wasn't the best k to be chosen and hence it was either a 4 or 5. Hence k means was performed on both the values of k and compared which one would tell us a better picture about the strains.

c) K-means on 4 Clusters:

Cluster 0 contained 222 samples, Cluster 2 with 130, Cluster 3 with 74 whereas Cluster 1 contained 2 samples which are outliers as they are clustered on the two products that have maximum votes. The observation that can be made is that the clusters 0 and 3 have an average value of 0 for CBD which really doesn't tell about the effectiveness of a product. And also, Cluster 0 has slightly more weighted negative side effects on average which for the goal of this analysis can be a factor to be considered.

Cluster 2 has CBD values ranging from 0 to 0.02% and a THC of 0.11% to 0.28% while cluster 3 has more votes. Even though cluster 2 is the clear choice here, it is interesting to have k=5 on this data to pick the best cluster with well defined features.

The box plot for these clusters can be seen in the Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Box Plot of the results of K-Means run on 4 clusters

d) K-Means on 5 Clusters:

Cluster 0: 78, Cluster 1:170, Cluster 2: 2, Cluster 3:56, Cluster 4:122

Figure 7 shows the box plot of the obtained results for 5 clusters.

Fig. 7. Box plot of 5 cluster K-Means

The data frame with the features and final clusters which encapsulates the strains and the features can be seen in Table below

	product_name	votes	thc_avg	CBD	Weighted_avg_score	cluster_number
0	Agent Orange	1.791045	0.250	0.00	0.229968	3
1	Alaskan Thunder	2.089552	0.195	0.00	0.255784	3
2	Alien Dawg	0.223881	0.175	0.01	0.172470	2
3	Alien OG	1.343284	0.230	0.00	0.349383	0
4	Allen Wrench	0.970149	0.205	0.00	0.532894	0

e) Conclusion:

- 1) Cluster 2 has two products listed under it primarily based on the highest votes can therefore be treated as outliers.
- 2) Cluster 1 has large number of samples with CBD =0 and the number of votes for cluster 1 strains is lower than any cluster.. The weighted negative side effects does not differ significantly.
- 3) Cluster 4 has roughly the same percentage of CBD and THC as that of Cluster 0 whereas the votes in cluster 4 is lower and weighted negative side effects is higher than Cluster 0.
- 4) Cluster 3 has CBD value ranging from 0 to 0.01 which is half found in Cluster 0 and Cluster 3 and also has more THC on average than the other clusters.
- 5) Cluster 0 has 78 products with CBD ranging from 0% to 2% and THC ranging from 11% to 27% with negative side effects ranging from 0 to 0.58 which is comparable to other clusters. The votes are in the range of 1.12 to 1.79.

Based on the above analysis, Cluster 0 is the most significant and the top 5 products with least negative side effects are shown in Table below

	product_name	Weighted_avg_score	thc_avg	CBD	votes
334	Purple Mr. Nice	0.005314	0.180	0.02	0.895522
222	Sugar Plum	0.015076	0.250	0.00	0.970149
52	Cheese Quake	0.020225	0.280	0.01	0.746269
196	SFV OG	0.038968	0.195	0.01	1.268657
14	Black Cherry Soda	0.049233	0.200	0.00	0.970149

2) *Fuzzy Clustering[8]:*

a) Introduction: The Fuzzy Clustering algorithm is a population based stochastic optimization technique which is used to find an optimal or near optimal solution to a clustering problem. Fuzzy clustering is a soft clustering technique. In fuzzy clustering, each data point is assigned a probability of it belonging to all clusters The highest probability defines which cluster the data point falls under.

b) Data Summary:

- Total number data points/observations - 440
- Missing Values - 12 rows
- Total Observations = 440-12 = 428

Features used for clustering - Chemical compositions of different strains (Sativa %, Indica %, THC % and CBD %), the negative side effects (Headache, Paranoid, Dizzy, Anxious) and votes.

c) Approach:

- Step 1: Handling missing values - Since the missing values are less than 3% of the total records, we choose to drop the missing records and not apply any imputation method.
- Step 2: Scaling input features - The negative side-effect columns are on a scale of 1 to 10 while the chemical compositions are on a scale of 0 to 1. To establish a uniform influence of all input features on the clustering technique, we are choosing to scale all feature onto a single logarithmic scale.
- Clustering (Code snippet)

```
clusters=fuzz.cluster.cmeans(df,3, 2, error=0.005, maxiter=1000, init=None, seed=None)
```

Method used: C-Means[12] algorithm from scikit-fuzzy

Parameters:

- Data (df) = 2d array/data frame
- c (value =3) = desired number of clusters
- m (value = 2) = membership weight
- Error= stopping criteria
- Maxiter = maximum number of iteration before achieving convergence

d) Results:

	Product_name	cluster1_weight	cluster2_weight	cluster3_weight	cluster
0	Agent Orange	0.005922	0.026311	0.967767	3
1	Alaskan Thunder	0.058121	0.860794	0.081085	2
2	Alien Dawg	0.676956	0.279066	0.043977	1
3	Alien OG	0.104709	0.750201	0.145090	2
4	Allen Wrench	0.013694	0.049680	0.936626	3

Fig. 8. Products clustered into 3

Strain/product are clustered into three groups. Each strain has a membership weights associated with all clusters. The highest weight defines the cluster into which the strain falls.

Cluster composition: Below table represents the number strains under each clusters.

TABLE XVI
NUMBER OF STRAINS IN EVERY CLUSTER

Cluster	Number of Strains
1	139
2	203
3	86

• **Clusters Vs. Side Effects**

It is seen that cluster 1 has the lowest side effects for Anxious, Paranoia, Dizzy and Headache, while cluster 3 has the highest side effects. A comparison of chemical composition of cluster 1 vs cluster 3 could provide insights in how chemical composition of a strain is dependent on the side effects it can cause.

• **Comparison of Cluster 1 Vs. Cluster 3**

Figure 9 shows the comparison.

Fig. 9. Box Plot: X-axis represents the cluster numbers (1 through 3), Y Axis represents the side-effect score

Fig. 10. Comparison of Cluster 1 Vs. Cluster 3

- 1) THC for cluster 1 ranges between 0.16 to 0.24 against 0.18 to 0.28 for cluster 3. This signifies that a higher composition of THC causes higher side effects.
- 2) CBD composition in cluster 1 is comparatively high compared to cluster 3. Cluster 1 has CBD ranging between 0 and 0.05, but cluster 3 has CBD range between 0 and 0.02.

Fig. 11. Sativa Vs. Indica with Cluster 1 and Cluster 3

Higher levels of indica and lower levels of sativa appear to have low side effects

3) DBSCAN (Density Based)[9]:

DBSCAN is Density Based Spatial Clustering of Application with Noise. It is a clustering algorithm that can handle clustering even if the dataset gives spherical plotting. This clustering algorithm is based on parameters, maximum radius of neighborhood and minimum number of points in the neighborhood, in short we can adjust the parameter distances to find the necessary cluster pattern we require.

a) **Problem Statement:** The goal of this model is to find medical products which are least in negative side effects for particular disorder PTSD through clustering. So the hypothesis statement for this problem made is that the calculated mean value of negative effects should be considerably lower.

b) **Data Summary:** In this model we have chosen features based on the correlation matrix. If two features show correlation, we cannot use them to identify pattern of products in clustering method. The below graph doesn't show correlation between side effects and the features selected are as in Figure 12

	3_DryMouth	3_Headache	3_DryEyes	3_Anxious	3_Paranoïd	3_Dizzy
31	10.0	0.6	5.2	0.0	3.4	1.4
36	10.0	2.6	5.6	0.0	3.4	1.3
43	10.0	0.0	8.4	1.0	2.2	0.9
47	10.0	1.2	5.5	0.0	5.8	1.2
52	8.3	0.0	2.2	10.0	2.7	2.7

Fig. 12. Selected Features

Fig. 13. Correlation graph between selected features

c) **Sativa & Indica Feature De-selection:** We attempted feature selection with Sativa and Indica but we found that both features are directly correlated and hence do not help in clustering methods and not relevant for clustering. Figure 14 below will help us in identifying correlation between medical compositions.

Fig. 14. Correlation graph between Medical Compositions

We can see direct correlation between Sativa and Indica. Hence these two features are not used as features when medical compositions are selected as features to find underlying pattern in the dataset.

d) Model: We have constructed the model and set the maximum radius of cluster point in a way that we see three different clusters formed, the yellow, green and light blue points stacked one over another. Figure 15 shows the same.

Fig. 15. DBSCAN output with 3 clusters

The counts per cluster formed as per below. -1 are the outliers, dark purple colored.

Counter(-1: 377, 1: 28, 0: 12, 2: 11)

So proceeding to find what products are found in the cluster we got these as below. Figure 16 shows the Cluster 0 products and as we can see, the clusters are formed perfectly around products with negative effects which had only the Dry Mouth as highest, 10. While all other effect are 0. So cluster zero provides products which had only Dry Mouth negative effect. And we can see the mean of negatives are 1.6667, least as our hypothesis statement.

	product_name	Sativa	Indica	thc_avg	CBD	3_DryMouth	3_Headache	3_DryEyes	3_Anxious	3_Paranoic	3_Dizzy	clusters	mean_negative_hypothesis
228	CBD Kush	0.50	0.50	0.045	0.07	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
493	Honey Bananas	0.50	0.50	0.165	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0	1.800000
1013	Yeti OG	0.30	0.70	0.200	0.03	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1339	Dakini Kush	0.30	0.70	0.205	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1371	Dr. Funk	0.20	0.80	0.000	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1405	Eran Almog	0.20	0.80	0.240	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1406	Erez	0.50	0.50	0.230	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1837	Purple Crack	0.85	0.15	0.165	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
1843	Purple Elephant	0.50	0.50	0.250	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
3202	South Indian	1.00	0.00	0.150	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
3271	Thai Lights	0.50	0.50	0.000	0.00	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667
3393	Avi	0.50	0.50	0.045	0.10	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0	1.666667

Fig. 16. Products falling into Cluster 0 after DBSCAN

Figure 17 below shows the products in clusters 1. Cluster 1 has 28 products and these are the first 10 products. We can see the clusters are formed around products which had all negative effects are valued zero.

	product_name	Sativa	Indica	thc_avg	CBD	3_DryMouth	3_Headache	3_DryEyes	3_Anxious	3_Paranoic	3_Dizzy	clusters	mean_negative_hypothesis
343	Dragon OG	0.7	0.3	0.190	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
521	Jesus	0.8	0.2	0.185	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
698	Pacific Blue	0.2	0.8	0.250	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
904	Strawberry Mango Haze	0.7	0.3	0.225	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
1095	Astroboy	0.7	0.3	0.190	0.01	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
1154	Blissful Wizard	0.5	0.5	0.330	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
1246	Captain America OG	0.5	0.5	0.240	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
2016	Super Sour Widow	0.5	0.5	0.180	0.11	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
2306	Blue Nina	0.5	0.5	0.175	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
2321	Blueberry Lamsbread	0.5	0.5	0.140	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
2471	Dawgfather OG	0.4	0.6	0.240	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0
2581	Frosted Freak	0.5	0.5	0.210	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1	0.0

Fig. 17. Products falling into Cluster 1 after DBSCAN

Finally, Figure 18 shows 11 products with considerably least mean of negative effects clustered together.

	product_name	Sativa	Indica	thc_avg	CBD	3_DryMouth	3_Headache	3_DryEyes	3_Anxious	3_ParanoId	3_Dizzy	clusters	mean_negative_hypothesis
434	Granddaddy Purple	0.50	0.50	0.235	0.01	10.0	0.8	4.6	0.0	0.9	1.6	2	2.983333
451	Green Crack	0.65	0.35	0.200	0.00	10.0	1.2	4.9	2.5	2.7	0.0	2	3.550000
533	Kandy Kush	0.50	0.50	0.180	0.00	10.0	1.8	4.6	0.0	0.4	2.1	2	3.150000
641	Nordle	0.50	0.50	0.080	0.05	10.0	0.0	4.6	0.0	1.3	1.3	2	2.866667
730	Pineapple Express	0.60	0.40	0.250	0.00	10.0	0.0	4.5	1.7	1.9	1.5	2	3.266667
747	Platinum Kush	0.10	0.90	0.185	0.01	10.0	0.0	4.4	3.0	3.1	1.6	2	3.683333
910	sunset sherbert	0.15	0.85	0.145	0.01	10.0	0.2	4.9	0.4	0.4	0.0	2	2.650000
1455	Goo	0.20	0.80	0.170	0.00	10.0	0.7	4.8	0.0	1.2	1.0	2	2.950000
2548	emperor cookie dough	0.22	0.78	0.410	0.04	10.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2	2.500000
2811	Lashkar Gah	0.00	1.00	0.120	0.00	10.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2	2.500000
3576	Mango Tango	0.30	0.70	0.240	0.00	10.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2	2.500000

Fig. 18. Products falling into Cluster 2 after DBSCAN

e) **Conclusion:** From our hypothesis, to find least negative effect products based on the average value of negative side effects. We arrived at statement that cluster 2 gives us marijuana products which are considerably least in negative effects with mean negative values around 2.5 to maximum of 3.0.

4) Latent Class Analysis[10]:

LCA is statistical method to find underlying relationship between categorical variables, how each feature clubs together and find pattern among them. In this case LCA model is attempted to find if there are any cases where the negative effect variables or medical compositions of product falls into familiar groups for PTSD disorder.

a) **Data Preparation:** For the LCA model to work, we need to make the variables of negative effects into categorical outcome starting with increment of 1. So we can write the formula with negative effects variables as predictors.

b) **Model Outcome & Interpretation:** We chose to run the model with three class options to see how the data population are distributed in group cases. And from Figure 19 we can identify that majority population of data are grouped into class 2 at 0.533, with class 1 and class 3 at 0.11 and 0.35 percentage.

The negative effect variables are grouped into ranks and classes based on their discrete values and seen in the output. For example, considering case with Dry Mouth variable, it has been grouped into 3 classes and 0-10 ranks. To interpret the data we have to pick a rank in the variables and compare it with 3 classes of all other variables. Taking rank 10 and class 3 among all variables we can see when Dry Mouth is highest, Dry Eyes are always populated in range of 3-6, Headache is always in range 0 and 1. With Paranoid and 0-3, Dizziness at 0-5 and Anxious at 0 when we take a product which gives headache at 10, highest.

Having seen most of the data population are grouped into class 2, we take a look at highest probable ranks among the variables. We find that when the Dry Mouth population are at rank 0, there are feeble other negative effects with majority population at 0 and occasional rank 10s for all other negative effects for the product. This can be confirmed by drop down selection criteria in the raw data file.

Fig. 19. LCA Output with three class options

Below are the obtained model selection scores.

```
## AIC(3): 12805.3
## BIC(3): 13685.1
## G^2(3): 3668.294 (Likelihood ratio/deviance statistic)
## X^2(3): 1728385 (Chi-square goodness of fit)
```

Fig. 20. Model Selection scores

c) **Conclusion:** The LCA model to identify groups and relations among given data is only based on behavioural data and distribution. And is not the same as other clustering models where clusters based on distances measured between variables. And there wasn't a method to derive product names grouped in class 2 from here. So this model is not suited for identifying products with least side effects but understanding the collective behaviour of negative effects of products in particular class / group. The higher Chi-score goodness of fit as in above screenshot determines goodness of the model selection.

5) Sparse Coding[11]:

a) **Introduction:** Sparse coding is a class of unsupervised methods for learning sets of overcomplete bases to represent data efficiently. Sparse coding also known as dictionary learning aims at finding a sparse representation of the input data in the form of a linear combination of basic elements as well as those basic elements themselves.

Learning a dictionary based on training is a much recent approach to dictionary design which is strongly motivated by recent advances in the sparse representation theory. In dictionary learning, the objective is to find a dictionary that provides the best representation for each examples in training set. Here, dictionary learning technique is used to build a overcomplete representation of data related to cannabis strains used to treat PTSD. This transformed data is used for unsupervised learning.

b) **Approach:** Over-complete representations can be more powerful than component analysis techniques. The attempt here is to learn a dictionary from the input data. The learned model is used to transform input data as a Sparse Representation and be fed into the unsupervised learning algorithms, thereby grouping cannabis strains into distinct clustering.

Features used for clustering - stain compositions (CBD%, THC %), negative side effects (Headache, Paranoid, Dizzy, Anxious) and votes received from users.

c) Code Snippet:

- Step 1: Dictionary Learning

```

from sklearn.decomposition import DictionaryLearning
dic_learn = DictionaryLearning(n_components=70, alpha=1, max_iter=1000, tol=1e-08,
                              fit_algorithm="lars", transform_algorithm="omp",
                              transform_n_nonzero_coefs=None, transform_alpha=None,
                              n_jobs=1, code_init=None, dict_init=None, verbose=False,
                              split_sign=False, random_state=None)

```

Parameters:

- n_components - Number of dictionary elements (a set of atoms) used to represent data through a sparse code
 - alpha - sparsity control parameter
 - max_iter - maximum number of iterations to perform
 - tol - tolerance for numerical error
 - fit_algorithm - lars algorithm is used here. It uses the least angle regression method to solve the lasso problem
 - transformation_algorithm - The algorithm used to transform the data is OMP. Orthogonal matching pursuit is used to estimate the sparse solution
 - n_jobs - number of parallel jobs to run
- Step 2: Fitting and transforming the input data

```

dic_data_fit=dic_learn.fit(data_input)#fit the input data
sparse_representation=dic_data_fit.transform(data_input)#transform the input data

```

- Clustering (K-means)

```

from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=5)
clusters = kmeans.fit(sparse_representation)

```

d) **Results:** Figure 21 shows the bar graph and box plots which are the results from our best clustering approach - k-means with sparse coding/dictionary learning. Along the X axis are the different clusters (0-3). The bar graph represents the number of strains in each clusters. The box plots presents a comparison of weighted side effect score and total reviews across clusters.

Fig. 21. Results of K-means with Sparse coding

- Cluster 1 constitutes of strains with relatively low side effect and high number of reviews. These are the strains that are popular and have low side effects.

- Cluster 2 has the lowest side effects. The reviews associated with these strains are also low. One of the reasons for low reviews could be that these strains could be relatively new. Nonetheless, considering the low side effects factor, this group certainly constitutes of strains that can be recommended for treating PTSD with low side effects.

D. Model Evaluation

Parameters used to compare models:

- Silhouette Coefficient
- Calinski-Harabaz Index
- Weighted negative side-effect score

1) **Silhouette Coefficient:** The Silhouette Coefficient is a clustering performance evaluation parameter, where a higher Silhouette Coefficient score relates to a model with better defined clusters. The best value is 1 and the worst value is -1. Values near 0 indicate overlapping clusters. The Silhouette Coefficient is defined for each sample/data point and is composed of two scores:

- 1) The mean distance between a sample and all other points in the same class.
- 2) The mean distance between a sample and all other points in the next nearest cluster

The Silhouette Coefficient s for a single sample is then given by Equation (6)

$$s = \frac{b - a}{\max(a, b)} \quad (6)$$

The Silhouette Coefficient for a set of samples is given as the mean of the Silhouette Coefficient for each sample.

2) **Calinski-Harabaz Index:** Calinski-Harabaz Index can be used to evaluate the model, where a higher Calinski-Harabaz score relates to a model with better defined clusters. For k clusters, the Calinski-Harabaz score s is given as the ratio of the between-clusters dispersion mean and the within-cluster dispersion:

$$s(k) = \frac{T_r(B_k)}{T_r(W_k)} \times \frac{N - k}{k - 1} \quad (7)$$

Where, B_k is the between group dispersion matrix and W_k is the within-cluster dispersion matrix 0.206

The weighted negative side effect score is a single feature which represents all the the side effects collectively (Dry Mouth, Dry Eyes, Headache, Paranoid, Dizzy, Anxious). Every individual strain has a negative side effect score and it ranges between 0 and 1. Mean value of this feature for the entire data set is 0.206. Every clustering algorithm aims at finding a population with low side effects and yields a sub-group with least side effect. A comparison of this subgroup across algorithm allows us to directly compare the performance of the clustering algorithm with respect to our main objective.

3) **Model Comparison Table:** Table XVII shows the model comparison table scored with Silhouette Coefficient, Calinski-Harabaz Index, and Mean of weighted side effect score.

TABLE XVII
MODEL COMPARISON TABLE

	K-Means Rank	DBSCAN Rank	Fuzzy Clustering	Sparse coding and K-Means	Sparse coding and DBSCAN	Sparse coding and Fuzzy Clustering
Silhouette Coefficient	0.35	-0.28	0.25	0.55	0.23	0.35
Calinski-Harabaz-Index	261.4	17.295	217.9	300.28	161.44	266.26
Mean of Weighted Side-effect score	0.098	0.076	0.058	0.057	0.081	0.078

K-means with sparse coding has the highest Silhouette coefficient value and Calinski-harabaz_index. This model has the highest accuracy and is considered for the final conclusion.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have ran multiple Machine Learning models and Statistical models on the Data which we had. Below is a summary of our findings across all models.

- 1) Our text analysis of review reveals that whenever a customer mentions PTSD in the reviews, there is strong correlation with other medical terms such as anxiety, depression, stress, insomnia and nausea. Specifically, anxiety and depression are the other top 2 keywords used in the PTSD reviews. In addition, when they mention PTSD and anxiety, they are more likely to talk about issues with insomnia, stress and depression.
- 2) Our statistical analysis indicates that within a 90% confidence interval, the following THC/CBD Ratios are statistically significant for PTSD. Two ranges, specifically GT2 (THC/CBD between 100-25.64) and GT10 (THC/CBD between 7.75-5.26) ranges have the highest correlations.

Bin	CBD/THC Ratio Range	Inverse- THC/CBD Ratio Range
GT2	(0.01 - 0.039)	(100 - 25.64)
GT3	(0.039 - 0.049)	(25.64 - 20.4)
GT4	(0.049 - 0.059)	(20.4 - 16.94)
GT7	(0.079 - 0.089)	(12.65 - 11.23)
GT10	(0.129 - 0.19)	(7.75 - 5.26)
GT13	(1.01 - 1.9)	(0.99 - 0.52)
GT14	(1.9 - 41)	(0.52 - 0.02)

- 3) We also discovered a correlation between THC, CBD and Review rating scores. If there is a 1% increase in THC of the strain, the product rating for that strain increases by 29.1% or 1.455 (on a scale of 1 to 5)
- 4) For a 1% increase in CBD/THC ratio of the product is in bin GT7, product rating decreases by 1.0222 (20.4%). For a 1% increase in CBD/THC in bin GT9, product rating decreases by 0.75 (15%).
- 5) Sparse coding technique along with K-means algorithm has the highest clustering accuracy. Amongst the four clusters generated by this unsupervised technique, two populations are of a significant importance. Cluster A constitutes of strains which are highly popular and also have comparatively low side effects. Cluster B constitutes of comparable strains with similar profiles, but with a lower side effects. The latter group constitute of strains ideal for treating PTSD, considering side effects as the key metric. This group has 58 strains. Figure 22 shows scatter plot presents this group with weighted side effect score plotted versus total of reviews associated with each strain.

Fig. 22. Scattered Plot of Cluster B

The mean of reviews and the mean of weighted side effect scores divide the scatter plot into four quadrants. Strains in the first quadrant are the ideal ones, having low side-effect score and high reviews. These strains are listed in Table XVIII.

TABLE XVIII
TABLE CONTAINING STRAINS WITH LOW SIDE-EFFECT SCORE AND HIGH REVIEWS

Sl. No	Strains	Total Reviews	Weighted Side-Effect Score
1	ghost-og	325	0.010
2	key-lime-pie	155	0.010
3	glass-slipper	157	0.012
4	cheese-quake	195	0.015
5	querkle	163	0.015
6	plushberry	198	0.017
7	dj-short-blueberry	182	0.018
8	snoop-s-dream	238	0.020
9	tangerine-haze	141	0.020
10	xxx-og	165	0.022
11	yoda-og	206	0.024
12	pure-kush	203	0.024
13	black-cherry-soda	214	0.025
14	ice	153	0.027
15	northern-lights-5	121	0.029

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